

THE EMERGENCE OF GENDER IN LINGUISTICS AND ITS TRANSITION TO THE CATEGORY OF CONCEPT

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Abstract: *The article focuses on the essence of the concept of gender, definitions of gender and gender research of the world and Uzbek scientists on gender, the current importance of gender, gender neutral language and its importance.*

Key words: *gender, sex, genealogy, gender neutral language, gender terms, grammatical gender, gender equality, gender coloring.*

Gender linguistics as an object of research in every science, the object of research in gender linguistics is gender. The concept of “gender” has been introduced into science to distinguish it from the concept of biological sex, “gender” that separates men and women based on them. “Gender” is a concept that defines the place and role of men and women in society.

These two terms need to be distinguished from each other. The term “gender” is derived from the Latin word “genus” in English, which means “gender”. There are two different interpretations of this concept will be done:

- 1) gender is a biological concept
- 2) social awareness

The first attempt to differentiate between gender and gender concepts was made in 1968 by University of California professor psychologist Robert Stoller and endocrinologist John Money.

According to sociologist Sofia Babayan, who was one of the first to use the term “gender” by Evig Goffman, “Gender” is a social concept. “The impeccable image of a women or a men is expressed in the diversity of the chronological and geographical environment, national traditions, religion, history, national mentality, and so on” the scholar writes. Gender is present in all social processes affecting women and men.

At present, gender equality in society, the state, education and family is one of the most important issues in the development of states. Therefore, gender should be studied as an important concept in development. The concept of gender in the field of science and research dates back to the 70th of the last century came in. By this time, various views and ideas were advanced by feminist scholars began to forward.

While the concept of gender, its formation and study requires research on the basis of interdisciplinary interdependence, it is necessary to study this concept from

the perspective of all disciplines. In their time, linguists, along with representatives of various disciplines, have paid special attention to this issue. Such scientists include V.Fon, Gumbold, A.A.Potebnya, Dj.Lakoff, T.A. Van Deyk, L.Push, E.S.Kubryikova, V.A.Maslova, Yu.S.Stepanov. We can include such scientists as A.Vezhbitskaya, A.V.Kirilina, D.V.Semenova. They have explored the concept of gender differently in their works on cognitive linguistics, linguocultural studies, and gender linguistics.

The concept of gender in terms of interdisciplinary interdependence has been widely studied by the Uzbek scholars. For example, K.R.Aliyeva's scientific work "Constitutional and legal framework for ensuring gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan" examines the constitutional formation of this concept in our country and its implementation in the legislation of our country. L.M.Tukhtasinov studied the linguocultural and gender features of slang words in literary texts on the basis of English and Uzbek materials. G.Ergasheva conducted research in terms of linguistic and extralinguistic factors in the formation of gender terminology in different language systems. Abdurahabova M.A. she has also conducted a number of studies and defended gender based articles and dissertations such as "Gender as the national grammatical category in linguistics".

From the above, it is clear that gender is a very broad and multifaceted concept, the field of study is endless.

Linguistics has different approaches to the concept of gender. Directly these aspects remain relevant in the teaching and learning of foreign languages. The main reason for this is that the concept of grammatical gender does not exist in the grammar of the Uzbek language. Because comparative teaching of grammar of foreign languages to language learners is a very effective and understandable method. But in order to teach the concept of grammatical gender, there is no such unit or category in Uzbek grammar. Therefore, it is important to give language learners a detailed understanding of this.

Genderology turned to the structures of language, recognizing their decisive role in the mechanisms of cultural representation of gender, which made it possible to illuminate areas of the construction and function of language that had not been explored before, and made a significant contribution to linguistics and the theory of speech behavior.

The importance of the gender in linguistics is not denied even by representatives of opposing views on feminism and its role in the creation of gender studies.

Androcentrism is directly related to the concept of linguistic sexism the use of language to criticize, humiliate, degrade women, which is correlated with racism, where discrimination is not based on gender, but on racial grounds.

Moreover, in recent years, the world community has become more like gender equality separate political, social, scientific experiences in this regard, knowing that the issues are relevant, laws, changes are being made. As a clear example the emergence of the concept of gender-neutral language on the world stage, and the need

to communicate using this language. We can cite the requirement to communicate using language. So what is a gender-neutral language? Gender-neutral language is a language that does not directly reflect the gender of a person, does not insult members of one gender or another one, and does not highlight them. Along with the term gender-neutral language, linguistics includes gender-neutral terms for all levels of language in general, terms and words were introduced and the existing ones were divided into separate categories.

When we learn foreign languages, we see that the language, culture, state and social changes, attitudes and norms of the language which are directly studied, enter our daily life in the state we want and do not want.

The study of gender terms also remains a requirement of the time. Indeed, in our country, too special attention is paid to gender equality. In this regard, along with mahalla and family institutions, the role of education, public education and higher education institutions is invaluable.

In conclusion, there is no doubt that gender studies have their own history of formation and have come a long way of development, formed as a new direction in linguistics and one of the promising areas of world science, which is of particular interest to experienced and young scientists. When should gender equality be achieved? When concepts such as gender, gender equality, gender terms can be achieved only when they are properly and fully explained to young people, not just young people but every member of society. Because this is the demand of the time. Living in step with the times is an indicator of our indifference to the future of our country.

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